

The Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence on Learning Outcomes of Islamic Religion and Characteristics of Students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar

M. Makbul¹, Ilyas Ismail, Wahyuni Ismail³, La Ode Ismail Ahmad⁴

¹Islamic Religious Education, Postgraduate UIN Alauddin Makassar

²Early Childhood Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, UIN Alauddin Makassar

³Islamic Religious Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, UIN Alauddin Makassar

⁴Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training, UIN Alauddin Makassar

ABSTRACT: The objectives of this research were: 1) to describe the level of students' emotional intelligence and students' characters on the subject of Islamic Religious Education at SMAN 5 Makassar. 2) To describe the level of students' spiritual intelligence and students' characters on the subject of Islamic Religious Education at SMAN 5 Makassar. 3) To describe the students' learning achievements and students' characters on the subject of Islamic Religious Education at SMAN 5 Makassar. 4) To examine the influences of emotional intelligence on students' learning achievements on Islamic Religious Education and Students' Characters in SMAN 5 Makassar. 5) To examine the influences of spiritual intelligence on students' learning achievements on Islamic Religious Education and Students' Characters in SMAN 5 Makassar. 6) To examine the influences of both emotional and spiritual intelligences on students' learning achievements on Islamic Religious Education and Students' Characters in SMAN 5 Makassar.

The methodological approach taken in this research was quantitative research methodology in which the ex post facto research design was employed. The scientific approach used by the researcher was psychological approach. The number of respondents of this study were 135 respondents in which proportional cluster random sampling was used. The data of this research were gained through a questionnaire and documentation format. The data were further analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics through the F test.

The results of this research indicated that the students' emotional intelligence at SMAN 5 Makassar was 17% at the low category, 64% at the medium category, and 19% at the high category. The conclusion from this research was that the score of students' emotional intelligence at SMAN 5 Makassar was at the medium category. In terms of the spiritual intelligence, it was apparent that the students' spiritual intelligence at SMAN 5 Makassar was 26% at the low category, 52% at the medium category, and 22% at the high category. Therefore, the students' spiritual intelligence at SMAN 5 Makassar was concluded to be at the medium category. In addition, the students' learning achievements at SMAN 5 Makassar were 25% at the low category, 64% at the medium category, and 10% at the high category. Thus, the score of students' learning achievements of the Islamic Religious Education Subjects and students' characters were at the medium category. Firstly, based on the results of data analysis of SPSS 24 on the students' emotional intelligence variable, it was found that the *tcount* was 12.474 and the *ttabel* value was at the significance of $0.05/2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$ because $tcount = 12.474 > 1.66$ with the significance value of 0.000. The significance value was < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. It could be concluded that the students' emotional intelligence has significant influences on students' learning achievements at Islamic Religious Education and Character Education subject. Secondly, based on the results of data analysis of SPSS 24 on the students' emotional intelligence variable, it was found that the *tcount* was 7.953 and the *ttabel* value was at the significance of $0.05/2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$ because $tcount = 8.711 > 1.66$ with the significance value of 0.000. The significance value was < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. It could be concluded that the students' spiritual intelligence has significant influences on students' learning achievements at Islamic Religious Education and Character Education subject. Thirdly, based on the results of data analysis of SPSS 24 on the students' emotional and spiritual intelligence variables, it was found that the *tcount* was 37.883 and the *ttabel* value could be seen on the statistic table with the significance of 0,05 with the formula of $f(k; n - k) = 2; 62 - 2 = 2; 60$. The results of *ftabel* obtained were 3,10. The results were $fcount > ftabel$ ($37,883 > 3,10$). Therefore, H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. It could be concluded that the students' emotional and spiritual intelligences have significant influences on students' learning achievements at Islamic Religious

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Education and Character Education subject. As implications of this research, it is expected for students at SMAN 5 Makassar to improve the learning achievements by having good time management as well as setting priorities for all kinds of activities at the school. In addition, in terms of spiritual intelligence, the students are expected to do and finish all the tasks and duties responsibly. In this case, the students are expected to improve their learning achievements by managing both their emotional and spiritual intelligences. In addition, it is expected also for teachers to continue to emphasize the decent values that can stimulate an increase in emotional and spiritual intelligence which have significant influences on students' learning achievements. Finally, for further researchers, it is also expected for future researchers to conduct further research related to academic procrastination, spiritual intelligence, and learning achievement. Several issues are recommended to be further explored such as decisions making difficulties, students' self-confidence, students' physical condition, students' fear of failure, and other related issues. Besides, further research related to the issue of improving the emotional and spiritual intelligence of students was also considered to be worth conducting.

KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence; Spiritual Intelligence; Students' Learning Achievements, Islamic Education Subject and Students' Character.

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence which includes emotional management intelligence which includes self-awareness, self-control, self-motivation, empathy and social skills, has a big share in supporting the learning success of students. Every student will get maximum learning outcomes if they are able to realize these emotional management skills, as well as spiritual intelligence, is also a very important part because students who have high spiritual intelligence will have direction and principles in an effort to develop themselves, even so this has not received full attention, especially in educational institutions. Referring to the facts that have been described

Student learning outcomes are the results achieved or obtained by students in the form of knowledge, skills and attitudes thanks to the experience and training that the individual has gone through. Learning outcomes are very important because they are in the form of data and values that are used as material to measure whether a lesson has been running as it should or still needs improvement and evaluation of all processes that are far from expectations.

Learning outcomes are influenced by the previous variables, namely emotional and spiritual intelligence, from the results of observations by researchers in July 2019 SMA Negeri 5 Makassar illustrates the variety of attitudes and behaviors of students, when receiving learning or outside learning. This difference can be seen in the activities of students showing various conditions, ranging from students who are indifferent to lessons, do not carry the Koran during Islamic Education subjects, do not participate in reading the Koran during class time and do not even enter during Islamic Education subjects, however on the other hand there are also those who are very enthusiastic about accepting students and outside the lesson consciously fill the time by memorizing the empty time even without direction and supervision from the educator.

The results of interviews with several students when asked about what religious activities he did at school answered that one of the students answered "I usually participate in activities carried out by the Ramnut Board (Youth Masjid Nurul Tarbiyah SMA 5), the reason is because I think it is a useful activity such as study, read the Koran together, practice lectures and so on, I think it is very useful for my future, both in the world and the hereafter. However, there are also students who have not shown good emotional and spiritual attitudes, such as one of the students' answers in the interview which said, "I don't like the teacher's method when studying in groups, I prefer to be alone when studying that's why I haven't joined the extracurricular activities at school.

Facts about learning outcomes are also illustrated from interviews with Islamic Religious Education subject teachers and character Mr. Ahwaluddin who explained that the learning outcomes of students were diverse and not a few students scored below the KKM as conveyed in the interview "in the last daily test there were no. a few who get a score below 75, maybe in every class I teach, even though I have used various learning methods and lesson plans "this information shows that there are students who get a score below 75 (minimum completeness criteria) but there are also students who score scores far beyond the KKM.

Seeing the reality that happened in SMA Negeri 5 Makassar, the researcher tried to link the theory of emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence that had been described previously in the hope that it could improve student learning outcomes. The theory that has been put forward about emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence explains that the higher the emotional and spiritual intelligence, the higher the learning outcomes that students can achieve, so that researchers try to conduct research that explains the relationship between variables so that in the future developments can be carried out in order to improve results. learn through increasing the emotional and spiritual intelligence of students

Based on the background of this problem, the researcher wants to do research to find out the reality of students related to emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence on learning outcomes of Islamic Religious Education and Character, so based on

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these arguments, make a study entitled *The Effect of Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence on Learning Outcomes of Religious Education. Islam and Characteristics of Students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar*. Literatur Review

A. Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the ability and skills related to the individual's ability to build relationships with the social environment, which describes the individual's sensitivity to social ethics, where a person can recognize his or her feelings and others, his ability to motivate himself, manage emotionally well and be able to build relationships with other people who shows someone has concern regarding ethics and morals, honesty, feelings, trustworthiness, politeness and tolerance

The five basic abilities in the theory of emotional intelligence in the theory of emotional intelligence according to Daniel Goleman, among them are:

1. Recognizing Your Emotional Self

Recognizing emotional self is an ability to recognize feelings as they occur. This ability is the basis of emotional intelligence, namely one's awareness of one's own emotions. Self-awareness makes us more aware of moods and thoughts about moods, if less alert, the individual becomes easily absorbed in the emotional flow and gets overpowered by emotion. Self-awareness does not guarantee emotional mastery, but it is one of the important prerequisites for emotional control so that individuals can easily control emotions (Daniel Goleman, 2003)

2. Managing Emotional

Managing emotional is a person's skill or skill in dealing with feelings so that they can be expressed appropriately, so that harmony is achieved within the individual. Keeping emotional concerns under control is the key to emotional maturity. Emotional excess that increases in a relatively long time will destabilize the individual. These abilities include the ability to calm yourself down, let go of anxiety, the anger of offense, and the ability to rise from adversity. (Daniel Goleman, 2003)

Suharsono quoted a hadith from the Prophet, narrated by Hakim and Ibn Hibban, which means "there are three things that if done will be protected by Allah in His care which is entered into His heaven, namely when given, he is grateful, if he is in power he is forgiving, and when he is angry he refrain (able to control himself)". (Suharsono, 2009)

3. Motivate Yourself

Achieving achievements must be achieved by having motivation within the individual, which means having the persistence to refrain from despair and controlling impulses, as well as having positive feelings of self-motivation, namely enthusiasm, passion, optimism and self-confidence. (Daniel Goleman, 2003)

4. Recognizing Other People's Emotions

The ability to recognize other people's emotions is also called empathy. According to Goleman, a person's ability to recognize other people or care, shows a person's ability to empathize. Individuals who have the ability to empathize are better able to accept other people's points of view, are sensitive to other people's feelings and are more able to listen to others. (Suharsono, 2009)

5. Building Relationships

The ability to cultivate relationships is a skill that supports popularity, leadership and success among people. Communication skills are the basic skills for successful relationship building. Sometimes humans find it difficult to get what they want and it is difficult to understand the wants and desires of others. (Daniel Goleman, 2003) A person who has the ability to build good relationships will be better able to communicate what his goals are and more readily understand what people are aiming for. other. (Suharsono, 2009)

B. Spiritual Intelligence

Referring to the understanding put forward by experts, it is concluded that spiritual intelligence is an intelligence which is the basis for the growth of self-esteem and moral values and a sense of belonging, even a person's ability to be more humane, and the ability to give meaning to worship so that it can be implemented in everyday life. Spiritual intelligence is the ability to develop a rational thinking attitude. The ability that stands out and is most essential in human (self, heart, soul, spirit) that grows since in the realm of spirits (believers), its potential is able to raise awareness of the meaning of obedience to moral values, norms, and affection for God and fellow creatures of Allah.

The concept put forward by Ary Ginanjar Agustian is that the meaning of Spiritual Intelligence (SQ) is the ability to give meaning to worship for every behavior and activity, through steps and thoughts that are natural, towards a complete human (hanief), and have a tawhid mindset. (integralistic), and has a principle only because of Allah "(Ary Ginanjar, 2003), Spiritual intelligence is the intelligence to deal with our behavior or life in the context of a broader and richer meaning, intelligence to judge that someone's life is more meaningful when compared to others. (Danah Zohar, 2001)

Spiritual intelligence is the ability to develop a rational thinking attitude. The ability that stands out and is most essential in human (self, heart, soul, spirit) that grows since in the realm of spirits (believers), its potential is able to raise awareness of the meaning of obedience to moral values, norms, and affection for God and fellow creatures of Allah. Thus, they will have the willingness or feeling to increase worship to Allah Almighty.

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C. Learning outcomes

Agus Suprijono explained that learning outcomes are patterns of actions, values, understandings, attitudes, appreciation and skills. Furthermore, Agus explained the learning outcomes in the form of:

1. Verbal information, namely the ability to express knowledge in the form of language, both oral and written.
2. Intellectual skills, namely the ability to present concepts and symbols. Intellectual skills consist of the ability to categorize, the ability to analyze-synthesis of facts, concepts and develop scientific principles. Intellectual skills are the ability to perform specific cognitive activities
3. Cognitive strategy, namely the ability to channel and direct its own cognitive activities. This ability includes the use of concepts and rules in solving problems.
4. Motor skills, namely the ability to carry out a series of physical movements in matters of affairs and coordination, so that physical movements are manifested automatically.
5. Attitude is the ability to receive certain objects, objects based on an assessment of that object Attitudes in the form of the ability to internalize and externalize values. Attitude is the ability to make values as a standard of behavior. (Agus Suprono, 2009)

Dimiyati and Mujiono explained that learning outcomes are "the effect of an interaction of learning actions and teaching actions. From the teacher's point of view, teaching actions end with a learning evaluation process. From the point of view of students, learning outcomes are the end of the cutting and the peak of the learning process. Learning outcomes are partly thanks to the actions of the teacher, an achievement of teaching goals. In another part, it is an increase in the mental abilities of students. The learning outcomes are divided into teaching impacts and accompaniment impacts. The impact of teaching is a measurable outcome, as stated in the report cards and the accompanying impact is the application of knowledge and abilities in other fields, a transfer of learning". (Dimayanti & Mujiono, 2002)

Referring to the explanation that has been described, it can be concluded that basically learning outcomes are the results achieved by a student after taking lessons or tests carried out by the teacher in class. In connection with this research, the intended learning outcomes are the values obtained by students after implementing the learning strategies referred to in this study.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The methodological approach taken in this research was quantitative research methodology in which the ex post facto research design was employed. The scientific approach used by the researcher was psychological approach. The number of respondents of this study were 135 respondents in which proportional cluster random sampling was used. The data of this research were gained through a questionnaire and documentation format. The data were further analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics through the F test.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This change is based on the results of data analysis obtained through descriptive and inferential data analysis, while the discussion will be described as follows;

1. Learners' Emotional Intelligence

Based on the data in the table, it was found that 17% of the emotional intelligence of students in SMA Negeri 5 Makassar were in the low category, 64% in the medium category, and 19% in the high category, so it was concluded that the emotional intelligence of students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar was in the medium category. This is the same as the research conducted by Sri Sumyati Ahmadi Putri with the research title The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Mathematics Learning Outcomes of Students at SD Inpres Bontomanai, Makassar City.

2. Students' Spiritual Intelligence

Based on the data in the table, it is found that 26% of the spiritual intelligence of students is in the low category, 52% is in the medium category, and 22% is in the high category. So it is concluded that the spiritual intelligence of students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar is in the medium category. This is the same as the findings of the research conducted by Muh Zulkifli with the research title The Effect of Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence on Learning Outcomes of Akidah Akhlak Students in class XI Madrasah Aliyah, Suragala District, Lombo Timur Regency.

3. Student Learning Outcomes

Based on the table above, it was found that 25% of the learning outcomes of the Islamic Religious Education subjects and Characteristics of students were in the low category, 64% in the moderate category, and 10% in the high category so that it was concluded that the learning outcomes of the Islamic Religious Education Subjects and Characteristics of students were included. medium category.

4. The effect of emotional intelligence on student learning outcomes in Islamic Education lessons

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Based on the results of data analysis using the help of the SPSS 24 application, it is obtained that linearity shows the calculated F data of 1.555 < F table 3,910 so it can be concluded that emotional intelligence has a linear relationship with learning outcomes.

The results of hypothesis testing (t test) for emotional intelligence variables obtained data if the independent variable emotional intelligence was able to predict the value of the dependent variable on student learning outcomes by 53.9%. The output above also explains that the number $R = 0.734$. So it can be concluded that there is a moderate relationship between emotional intelligence and student learning outcomes. In addition, based on the results of processing with SPSS 24 it was obtained -3.777 and the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of $0.05 / 2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$ because $= 1.66 < 12.474$ Significance value 0,000. Significance value < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), then it is rejected and accepted.

If it is related to the notion of emotional intelligence itself, theoretically it has been explained that the ability of students to control aspects of self-awareness, manage emotions, motivate themselves, empathy and build relationships is very supportive of student learning outcomes, especially Islamic Religious Education Subjects and Character. Students who are skilled in managing their emotions well will give students the ability to learn, including Islamic religious education material and character, those who are able to recognize emotions, manage emotions and have a relationship with their friends, really help them understand and solve problems in learning.

The results of this study reveal that students who have emotional intelligence where they are able to recognize their own emotions well, manage emotions, recognize other people's emotions, have empathy and the ability to build relationships is very beneficial for students in an effort to improve their learning outcomes.

5. The influence of spiritual intelligence on student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar.

Based on the results of data analysis using the SPSS 24 application, it was obtained data of 1,280 < of 3,910, it can be concluded that spiritual intelligence has a linear relationship with student learning outcomes data.

From the Model Summary table, the value $= 0.692$ means that the independent variable of spiritual intelligence is able to predict the value of the dependent variable on student learning outcomes by 69.2%, the remaining 30.8% is explained by other factors. The output above also explains that the R number is 0.793. So it can be concluded that there is a strong relationship between spiritual intelligence and student learning outcomes.

Based on the results of processing with SPSS 24, it was obtained 7,953 and the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of $0.05 / 2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$. Because $= 8,711 > 1.66$. The significance value is 0.000. Significance value < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), then it is rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that spiritual intelligence has a significant effect on student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education.

The results of this study reveal that students who have good spiritual intelligence, namely students who are able to be flexible, have a high level of awareness, the ability to deal with suffering, and the ability to understand life inspired by vision and values are very useful for students in an effort to improve their learning outcomes.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability of students to find meaning and motivation or encouragement from within students should provide positive things for students themselves, such as motivation to provide great enthusiasm for students to get proud achievements.

6. The effect of emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence together on the learning outcomes of students in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar.

Based on the Model Summary table, the value $= 0.562$ means that the independent variables of emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence are able to predict the value of the dependent variable on student learning outcomes of 56.2%, the remaining 43.8% is explained by other factors. The output above also explains that the R number is 0.750. So it can be concluded that there is a sufficient or moderate relationship between emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence on student learning outcomes.

Based on the results of processing with SPSS 24, it was obtained 37.883, the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of 0.05 with the formula $f(k; n - k) = 2; 62 - 2 = 2; 60$, so that the amount is 3.10. Value $> (37,883 > 3,10)$ then rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence affect student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education lessons.

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded in this study that emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence together have a significant influence on student learning outcomes, in this case emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on learning outcomes of Islamic Religious Education and Character. Likewise, spiritual intelligence has a positive and significant effect on learning outcomes of Islamic Religious Education and Character on students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar.

Through the elaboration of the results of this study, it can be understood that both emotional and spiritual intelligence have a significant effect on student learning outcomes, this is in line with the theoretical studies described earlier in this study.

In the discussion section has been described by Sarlito W. Sarwono that emotional intelligence is the most important psychological factor in the learning process of students, because it determines the quality of student learning. The higher the

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intelligence level of an individual, the greater the individual's success in learning. Conversely, the lower the individual intelligence level, the more difficult the individual is to achieve learning success.

In research conducted by researchers at SMAN 5 Makassar, it shows that students who have a good average value of emotional intelligence tend to have good learning outcomes as well, one of the most important things from the aspect of emotional intelligence that needs to be considered is looking at the dynamic context of students. at the high school level, especially at SMAN 5 Makassar, namely the self-motivating aspect, students who are able to recognize emotions, manage emotions, motivate themselves, recognize other people's emotions and foster relationships will feel more comfortable with the nuances of learning at school which tend to use a collaborative approach that orientates participants students to be able to learn together with their respective characteristics and personalities.

The dimension of emotional intelligence really supports students in learning, where to be able to work in groups collaboratively, students must at least have the aspects contained in emotional intelligence.

Spiritual intelligence also has a special portion in increasing student learning outcomes, where this spiritual intelligence is the ability to find meaning and see everything on the basis of worship to Allah Almighty. so that students who have a high average spiritual intelligence tend to have relatively better learning outcomes than low ones.

If someone has spiritual intelligence, it will lead to a deep understanding of the realities of life, so that it will be able to help someone communicate and adapt well to fellow humans. The level of a person's spiritual intelligence will affect the level of intellectual intelligence and emotional intelligence, because spiritual intelligence can synergize the two intelligences, namely intellectual and emotional. Spiritual intelligence is the intelligence to face and solve problems and place the value of human life behavior in the context of a broader and richer meaning. Therefore, people will try to make good use of everything and not harm others, so it can be judged that one's actions or way of life are more meaningful than others.

Spiritual can be interpreted as things that are uplifting or related to spirit, so that you have positive attitudes and behaviors towards others, from this understanding, spiritual can be interpreted as something related to human ability to arouse enthusiasm, while spirituality is the basis for the growth of self-esteem, values, morals, and a sense of belonging.

A person with high spiritual intelligence tends to be a dedicated leader, that is, someone who is responsible for bringing higher visions and values to others, and providing guidance on how to use them. (Danah Dohar, 2001)

Referring to the understanding put forward by experts, it is concluded that spiritual intelligence is the ability to develop a rational thinking attitude. The ability that stands out and is most essential in human (self, heart, soul, spirit) that grows since in the realm of spirits (believers), its potential is able to raise awareness of the meaning of obedience to moral values, norms, and affection for God and fellow creatures Allah swt. thus will have the willingness or taste to increase worship to Allah Almighty.

The theoretical description of spiritual intelligence clearly explains that students who have spiritual intelligence will think that the learning activities they carry out are not merely routine but also a way to increase worship to Allah SWT. considering that the dynamics of students from a spiritual side has become very crucial considering that during the transitional period from childhood to adulthood, various new problems are starting to appear, so that the initial foundation is related to life goals and interpreting what is done is very important for participants to understand students.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions in this study are:

1. The emotional intelligence of students in SMA 5 Negeri obtained 17% low category, 64% medium category, and 19% high category. The conclusion from the table above is that the emotional intelligence score of students in SMA Negeri 5 Makassar is in the moderate category
2. The emotional intelligence of students in SMA 5 Negeri Makassar is 26% in the low category, 52% in the medium category, and 22% in the high category. So that the spiritual intelligence of students at SMA Negeri 5 Makassar is included in the medium category.
3. The learning outcomes of students at SMA 5 Negeri Makassar are 25% in the low category, 64% in the medium category, and 10% in the high category. The learning outcomes scores of the Islamic Religious Education Subjects and the Characteristics of students were in the medium category.
4. Based on the results of processing the emotional intelligence variable with SPSS 24, it was obtained 12.474 and the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of $0.05 / 2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$ because $= 12.474 > 1.66$. The significance value is 0.000. Significance value < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), then it is rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education lessons.
5. Based on the results of processing with SPSS 24, it was obtained 7.953 and the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of $0.05 / 2 = 0.025$. The results obtained for $t(0.025; 133) = 1.66$. Because $= 8,711 > 1.66$. The significance

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value is 0.000. Significance value <0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), then it is rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that spiritual intelligence has a significant effect on student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education.

6. Based on the results of processing with SPSS 24, the value is 37.883, the value can be seen in the statistical table for a significance of 0.05 with the formula $f(k; n - k) = 2; 62 - 2 = 2; 60$, so that the amount is 3.10. Value $> (37,883 > 3,10)$ then rejected and accepted. So it can be concluded that emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence affect student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education lessons.

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